

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

KAZAKHSTAN'S PERFORMANCE IN THE INTERNATIONAL PIRLS STUDY

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Abstract

This article analyzes the indicators and findings of the PIRLS International Reading Literacy Progress Study of Kazakhstan. Kazakhstan participated in two cycles of the PIRLS International Progress in Literacy Study. Downward dynamics was observed among the results of the study. The factors that influenced the dynamics and the order of work performance in Kazakhstan are shown.

Keywords: PIRLS, Kazakhstan, reading literacy, learning, school, grade 4.

PIRLS, the International Progress in Literacy Study, is one of the major studies of the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA). Conducted every five years since 2001 by the TIMSS International Study Center and Boston College's PIRLS, PIRLS is a global standard for assessing trends in fourth graders' academic achievement [1].

The PIRLS survey measures students' reading literacy levels. Through a comprehensive study, countries will be able to gain information about students' academic literacy and identify weaknesses. The PIRLS study has also influenced many countries, forcing them to change their educational process.

Kazakhstan has been participating in the PIRLS study since 2016. During these years, influenced by the research, it has played a crucial role in modernizing Kazakhstan's education system. It has allowed the country to obtain reliable data on the reading skills of fourth-

graders, including educational inequalities and the impact of contextual factors on student performance. This data helps the country identify the strengths and weaknesses of its education programs and provides insights into the development of new teaching methods and technologies to improve students' learning skills. The 2016 PIRLS National Report provides key recommendations for improving the quality of elementary language and literature education. Subjects in the PIRLS format have been introduced in the curriculum of a number of schools. In addition, based on the results of international comparative studies, the Ministry of Education has set a number of tasks for the formation of school-library activities to increase students' interest in learning and support learning [2].

The educational objectives of the subjects "Kazakh language and literature" and "Russian language and literature" in Kazakhstan today meet the criteria of the evaluation concept of the study.

Learning objectives for the subject "Kazakh language and literature"/"Russian language and literature", grade 4	PIRLS assessment framework
- Finding information (text, feelings, diagrams, table, map, chart)	• Finding information given in explicit form
- formulating conclusions; - predict the development of the story from the beginning or end of the text; - determine the author's attitude to a character, compare his or her own and the author's assessment; - determine the theme and main idea on the basis of text analysis; - compare the actions of characters by analogy/contrast, clarify one's opinion with words and sentences in the text;	- formulate direct conclusions; - formulate conclusions to compare, describe, and predict; - explain and combine ideas and information to determine the main idea; - recognize the overall message or theme of a text; - compare textual information; - connect and explain the events of a story and describe the reasons for characters' actions and feelings;
- compare a character's actions and behavior with their own life experience; - describe character, experiences, identify the author's ways of creating them; - recognize in the text a comparison, image, epithet, hyperbole, metaphor and use them in speech;	- understand the meaning of certain features of language (e.g., metaphor);
- distinguish polysemous words, phraseological phrases, understand their role in a certain context and use them in speech [3].	- Evaluate the purpose of adding a particular element to a conversation [4].

This indicates that there has been a change in the education system since the 2016 PIRLS study. The learning objectives allow students to improve their reading literacy and prepare for the PIRLS study.

However, these changes are not enough to show students' reading literacy at a high level. Let's compare

Kazakhstan's performance in the two PIRLS surveys. On a point scale, Kazakhstan dropped by 32 points compared to 2016. In the ranking of countries, Kazakhstan in 2021 fell 11 positions lower than in 2016. The existence of such an indicator is influenced by many factors.

PIRLS 2021 assessed reading comprehension according to the PIRLS 2021 Learning Assessment Framework (Chapter 1 in the PIRLS 2021 Learning Assessment Framework). The PIRLS Learning Assessment Framework is updated each cycle to ensure that research on learning and educational development remains at the forefront through checks by the PIRLS Learning Development Group (RDG) and National Research Coordinators (NRCs). This remains relevant and relevant to PIRLS practice and teaching policy. However, PIRLS is a trend study and the underlying organization has remained unchanged throughout the cycles [5].

PIRLS 2021 incorporated two significant changes to the assessment of international learning in fourth grade: a shift to quantitative assessment and the introduction of a cohort response design.

The PIRLS 2021 cohort adaptive design provides better cross-country measurement by better matching assessment complexity and student achievement levels. The cohort adaptive design is based on texts and tasks at three levels of difficulty-complex, medium, and easy-that are organized into booklets of two levels of difficulty. The more complex booklets include complex to medium texts and items, and the less complex booklets contain simple to medium texts and items. All booklets are distributed in each country, but countries with high average student achievement may provide complex booklets to a higher percentage of students (70%), while countries with low average student

achievement may provide a higher percentage of students [5].

In Kazakhstan, the concept of adaptive testing is one of the areas that is not considered, so students were not prepared for this format. The second aspect is the transition to digital assessment. In Kazakhstan, only from January 1, 2022, the subject "Digital Literacy" is introduced in the curriculum of elementary school. So it shows that computer literacy of students in the PIRLS 2021 study was very low. Students can make mistakes even pressing basic computer buttons.

PIRLS 2021 will take place during the global outbreak of the infectious disease "COVID-19". This also affected the results. The students received their education online. Until then, there was no practice of online education in Kazakhstan. This led to a decrease in the educational level of students. Lack of Internet in rural areas, insufficient funds for Internet access. Due to these inconveniences, the educational process was interrupted.

According to the UN Concept Note: Education in the era of COVID-19 and beyond August 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic caused the biggest disruption in education systems, affecting about 1.6 billion students in more than 190 countries. all continents. The closure of schools and other educational institutions affected 94 percent of the world's student population, compared to 99 percent in low- and low-middle-income countries [6].

According to the results of the PIRLS 2021 survey of Kazakhstan on the socio-economic status of the family 18% showed low social status, 71% - average social status, 11% - high level of social status. If we compare them with the UN data, we can see that in this country the average level of socio-economic conditions prevails, and this has an impact on the educational process. Having multiple children in one family and not having enough gadgets for all became a major problem during COVID-19.

Another problem that continues to hamper PIRLS research. Actual problems of native language proficiency, conscious learning of Kazakh language. "It is the duty of every citizen of the Republic of Kazakhstan to study the state language, which is a very important factor in grouping the people of Kazakhstan" [7]. Despite this, more than half of pupils in Kazakh classes cannot speak Kazakh fluently. This indicator has a great impact on students' reading literacy. One of the reasons for the spread of this situation is that all the information that children receive in the information space is in foreign languages. This is also an indicator of the lack of quality information digital base in the Kazakh language. There is no quality content in the Kazakh language, it is difficult to find interesting animations that attract the attention of students.

The reasons for the low dynamics of the current PIRLS study in Kazakhstan were mentioned. Currently works are underway to address the above issues. For example. In order to awaken students' desire to learn and turn reading into a skill. schools need to address the development of functional literacy and the development of Kazakhstani patriotism through the following important project activities:

"Book. Country. Spirit". Mass public movement "Reading Nation"; 2. "Bookcrossing". Organization of special places for book exchange; 3. "Precious Gift". Organization of a charitable campaign for voluntary delivery of books to libraries; 4. "Library - Center of Knowledge". Organization of meetings of students with library staff, literary evenings in student houses and student leisure centers [8].

In addition, in 2023-2024 academic year in Kazakhstan started the project "8 Minute Reading". The purpose of this project is to familiarize schoolchildren with reading books and to develop the child's reading literacy.

In conclusion, we note that Kazakhstan is working to improve functional literacy, including reading literacy. There are problems, ways to solve them are being considered. PIRLS, pandemic has revealed weaknesses in the sphere of education in Kazakhstan. Thanks to this, an education system corresponding to world standards will be created. Kazakhstan has learned the importance of reforming new ideas and programs in the field of education.

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